

WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT IN ENUGU, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study examined waste management system in Nigeria focusing specifically on assessment of waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across in Nigeria; ascertain core challenges bedeviling waste management practices in Nigeria such as funding limitations, inadequate technology, policy implementation gaps, and socio-cultural factors as well as proffering solutions to the various challenges affecting waste management practices in Nigeria. Survey research was adopted as the methodology of the study using the population of Enugu metropolis. This study discovered that solid waste generation and management is a problem in developing nations and even in some developed ones but the consequences are more adverse with developing nations like Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that addressing the challenges of waste management in Nigeria necessitates the need for an all-inclusive waste management approach. Proper implementation and enforcement of waste management laws and policies, review of the current waste management legislation across the states of the nation, private-public participation should be encouraged, adequate budgetary provision, periodic comprehensive appraisal of the environmental effect of waste management practices, knowledge sharing on global issues affecting ecological conditions and sustainable development.*

Keywords: *Waste Management, Nigeria, Challenges, Policy Implementation, Sustainable Development*

1. Introduction

Wastes are part and parcel of human existence as almost every human activity is associated with one kind of waste or another. It is based on this note that Aniekan and Ikechukwu (2016) noted that waste is an inevitable by-product of human activities. It takes the form of solid, liquid and gas. Waste, over the past years, has been defined and considered as a matter that has no monetary or economic value and discarded or thrown away if it fails to meet its primary function. Recent advances in technology and a better understanding of materials have been applied in the reduce, reuse, and recycling process

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that adds both monetary and economic value to waste matter while simultaneously mitigating the adverse effects of unchecked waste in the environment (Ikpe, Owunna & Agho, 2019).

Nigeria generates all types of waste, and a large portion of the waste generated is indiscriminately disposed in the environment, even by waste collectors. It is on this note that Ndou and Rampedi (2022) asserted that challenges resulting from the management of municipal solid waste (MSW) are on the rise globally due to MSW mismanagement, rural–urban migration, population growth, commercial, industrial, and socioeconomic activities, leading to increased volumes of MSW and unplanned or a lack of functional municipal solid waste management (MSWM) facilities, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Nigeria’s poor waste management system has seen it exposes her citizens to public health risks and environmental dilapidation. The health risk posed by the indiscriminate waste disposal is seen by the “black death” epidemic of the 14th century that killed nearly half the population of Europe. Its cause was from the unhygienic environment which aided the spread of the bacteria called “Yersinia pestis” by infected rodents and flea that find refuge in such environments (Gan & Okojie, 2013).

The implication of improper waste management can result in adverse risk conditions such as ground water contamination, air pollution, increase in insect vectors and diseases transmitted by them, poor environmental aesthetics, attraction of vermin and pests, breeding grounds for disease spreading vectors such as “*mastomys natalensis*” (responsible for Lassa fever), emission of Green House Gases (GHGs) such as methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Ikpe, Ebunilo & Okovido, 2018). For example, decomposition of organic waste matter in open dumpsite releases poisonous gases such as hydrogen sulphide, ammonia, and offensive odour into the atmosphere; toxic leachate is also formed from the decomposition of open dumpsite waste (organic and inorganic) that mixes with water, polluting groundwater and surface water (Ikpe, Ndon & Adoh, 2019). The exposure of humans to waters contaminated by open waste dumping can lead to diseases like diarrhoea, cholera, skin diseases, malaria, tuberculosis, and cancer from the pathogens in the contaminant (Samuel, Davou, Juliet & Ruth, 2016). Previous epidemiological studies have found that two main health outcomes -cancer and congenital malformations– are associated with waste exposure to dumpsites (Mavropoulos & Newman, 2015).

Waste management practices in Africa at large and Nigeria specifically leaves much to be desired. There are diverse factors that are responsible for this fact. For instance, Aliyu & Amadu, 2017; Saghir & Santoro (2018) noted that in Africa, rapid urban growth has exacted massive pressure on cities, towns and surrounding areas. This has led to increased urban waste generation leading to health hazards, underground water pollution, and affected air and aesthetic qualities (Mazhindu et al., 2012). The inability to properly manage these wastes generated in developing countries such as Nigeria creates great concern (Amasuomo & Baird, 2016). Nigeria, with a population exceeding 180 million (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018) is one of the largest producers of solid waste in Africa (Bakare, 2020).

Despite a host of policies and regulations, solid waste management in the country remains a huge challenge to the authorities, stakeholders and the entire public. This is based on the premise that the different components that make up an effective waste management system are either not being put in place or are inadequately implemented or not put into good use. This study is set to critically evaluate waste management system in Nigeria. To effectively address this concept, the study is set to center on the following objectives: assess waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis; ascertain core challenges bedeviling waste management practices in Nigeria such as funding limitations, inadequate technology, policy implementation gaps, and socio-cultural factors; proffer solutions to the various challenges affecting waste management practices in Nigeria.

2.0 Review

2.1 Waste Management Practices in Nigeria

Waste management entails generation, collection, handling, transfer, disposal, reuse, recycling, reclaim and auditing of waste at a minimal cost (Demirbas, 2011). These practices differ from nation to nation depending on the waste sources, types, and characteristics (Coker, Achi, Sridhar & Donnett, 2016). It plays a vital role in nature's ability to sustain life within its capability. In many developing nations of the world, it has become a recurrent challenge, especially in urban areas. The land use is greatly affected by urbanization and when out of control results in the advent of unauthorized structure and informal settlements that are common within the nation. Ultimately this affects the city blueprint and services like waste collection and subsequently causing indiscriminate dumping of refuse (Ferronato & Torretta, 2019).

Waste represents a vital developmental and environmental issue; it is an inevitable result of human activity. In recent times, humans generate more waste, not only because of an increase in population but also due to the change in the pattern of consumption and various composition of waste (Udo, Esezobor, Afolalu, Onovo, Ongbali & Okokpuji, 2018). Thus, necessitating the need for a shift towards waste reduction and away from waste deposition at the dumping site (McAllister, 2015). Waste generation in Nigeria is on the increase due to the rise in population resulting from the techno-economic development in cities and the pattern of production and consumption of materials (Gutberlet, 2018). Nigeria estimated waste generation rate per capital per day is between 0.65kg and 0.95kg. This constitutes over fifty percent of the total amount of waste generated in sub-Saharan Africa (Edet & Maduabuchi, 2019). The current waste management practices in the nation are fast becoming a national issue and unsustainable, leading to apparent environmental risk (Ike, C. C., Ezeibe, Anijiofor & Nik Daud, 2018). Numerous studies have identified the impacts of poor waste management practices to include environmental pollution, energy consumption, climate change, and environmental degradation (Afolalu, Oladipupo, Bose, Abioye, Adejuyigbe, Ajayi & Ongbali, 2019).

2.2 Ethical Issues and Legal Frameworks on Waste Management Practices

Nigeria is one of the major producers of waste in sub-Saharan Africa with a population of over 200 million. In spite of policies and regulations, waste management practices in the nation are worrisome each passing day. Over 32 million tons of solid waste were generated annually, of which one-third of the waste generated is collected (Ayodeji, 2021). Indiscriminate disposal has resulted in blockage of drains, and obstruction of water bodies. Inappropriate collection and disposal of wastes are gradually leading to an environmental disaster as the nation presently lacks sufficient budgetary requirements for implementing integrated waste management systems across the states (Ernestina, Adetola & Odufa, 2014).

In most of the developing countries like Nigeria, laws, policies, statutes, and regulations on waste management are underdeveloped, and even the existing ones are poorly implemented. Generally, laws involving waste management were mainly formulated and articulated. The poor state of waste management systems in the nation reflects its laws and policies (Opodo & Oluwatayo, 2016). There are several loopholes in the governmental policies on waste management, though the public is encouraged to partake in the monthly clean-up exercise. However, the government has failed in providing disposal sites as a form of compliment for the efforts of the citizens. In some of the states in the nation, it has been reported that there is no articulate piece of legislation that deals with waste management, and it has been argued that it's owing to a weak institutional, legal framework, and administration of policies. Most government policies that are in place lack strategies for actualization. In addition, a review of the legislative aspect of waste management has been suggested in other to work towards achieving set objectives on sustainable waste management. Furthermore, an all-inclusive management approach has been proposed which entails waste prevention, reuse, reclaim, recycle, composting, and generation of energy. Despite some good policies that are in place, proper implementation remains a significant challenge; for instance, a comprehensive environmental impact assessment is meant to be submitted during project planning before approval. However, this critical regulation is frequently overlooked. Several authors have criticized the implementation and enforcement of environmental laws in Nigeria. Enforcement of environmental laws remains an issue of concern, control, and management of environmental legislation that has achieved very little success (Alabi, Kasim & Lasisi, 2020). Some of the enforcement challenges in Nigeria have socio-political and economic nuances. In other to make sustainable waste management, appropriate policy and proper planning, in addition to enforcement of waste management legislation, must be implemented (Ezeudu, 2019).

2.3 Application of systems approach to achieving a cleaner and sustainable environment:

The strive to have a clean and habitable environment has become a common challenge in man's habitat. This has been because of complex activities engaged in by man, leading to various pollutant effects which are hazardous to the environment (Oguntunde et al. 2014). It is a common place to note that the

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effects of man's interaction with the environment, especially the urban areas where population density is high, have yielded challenging effects in terms of sanitation issues to the habitat (Levy & Dinopoulos, 2016).

The nexus of man's interactions with the habitat in his strive for survival is a historical perspective to the generation of waste and pollutant objects that affect our environment and life in general (Leontiev, 2014). These challenges have also resulted in global concerns such as climate change which tend to pose critical threat to sustainability of man's habitat (Barbante et al. 2017). A fundamental source of pollutant waste is the household, which generates different items of wastes ranging from biological wastes, and other wastes items related to human inhabitant activities in the environment (Palabiyik, et al. 2015). The critical challenges posed by the waste generation activities coupled with man's inability to develop a sustainable waste management approach that can effectively address the aftermath effects result in the pollutant danger in the environment (Wong et al. 2018).

Effective waste management is therefore a critical issue that calls for due attention from the relevant authorities and the stakeholders concerned to the issues of enhancing a cleaner environment, especially in residential locations that have population density. The effects of environmental pollution have resulted in challenges ranging from health issues to outright degradation on the affected environment (Omole & Longe, 2008). For instance, China is faced with massive air pollution in recent times that has led to death in an alarming number (Rhode & Muller 2015). Similarly, Zabbey et al. (2017) observed that the activity of oil and gas exploration firms in generating toxic waste in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria has created devastating effects, resulting in critical concerns for man's survival. This narrative tends to balance man's activities and strive for his survival with adequate attention to the end-to-end effects on the environment, to have a sustainable habitat.

Many approaches have been adopted by the public sector to address waste issues in the environment at different times (Beard & Green, 2014). For example, many state government authorities in Nigeria adopt the end of month environmental sanitation exercise. This can help the project of environmental cleaning via the involvement of both households and the government agencies to engage in environmental cleaning to address waste management issues. However, these efforts have been speculated to be inadequate in addressing the challenges of having a clean and sustainable environment. This level of waste management challenges, especially in residential locations, has made the government agencies take a step further by embarking on further cleaning exercises, other than the monthly general sanitation (Nwaka, 2020). Furthermore, researchers such as Olukanni and Mnenga (2015) suggest a bottom-up approach embedded in cooperation among the actors in environmental waste management in Nigeria, with due regulatory attention to land use and address the complexity in urban waste management. Particularly, Barredo et al. (2019) argued that studies on environmental sustainability issues in developing countries would enhance the need to pay more attention to urban

growth and economic development issues. Nevertheless, it seems that despite these efforts, the achievement of a sustainable approach to manage environmental waste remains an ongoing challenge necessitating the search for a more effective approach to address the issue in human activities on environmental sustainability.

3.0 Methodology

Survey research was adopted in this study due to the fact that surveys are important in explaining the traits of a large population as they make sure a more accurate sample to gather targeted results in which to draw conclusions and make important decisions. Also the anonymity of surveys allows respondents to answer with more candid and valid answers (<https://www.snapsurveys.com/blog/4-main-benefits-survey-research/>).

3.1 Population and Sample Size

Enugu metropolis, as recorded by the 2006 census, comprises approximately 722,664 residents distributed among three main Local Government Areas—Enugu North, Enugu South, and Enugu East. Enugu North and Enugu South each account for 259,000 and 267,000 residents respectively, while Enugu East comprises about 196,664 residents. Given this substantial and diverse urban population, it is essential to capture the variety of experiences and practices related to waste management across these distinct geopolitical areas.

For this study, a research population of 212 has been deliberately selected to represent the broader community. By stratifying this population proportionally across Enugu North, South, and East, the study ensured that each area's unique demographic and socio-economic characteristics are accurately reflected. This stratified approach not only enhances the representativeness of the 212 units but also makes the study more manageable in terms of data collection and analysis while still capturing the necessary diversity.

The decision to focus on 212 units is grounded in practical considerations, balancing resource constraints with the need for robust and meaningful insights into waste management practices.

3.2 Study Population and Sample Size

The population of the study comprised of the management and staff of both quoted pharmaceutical and non-quoted firms in Nigeria, pharmacists, and selected individuals.

The population distribution is shown below:

Table 3.2.1: Population Distribution Table

S/N			Population
1.	Enugu North	259,000	76
2.	Enugu South	267,000	78
3.	Enugu East	196,664	58

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5.	Total	722, 664	212
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Source: Field Survey, 2025

The Cochran formula was adopted in determination of the sample size of the study. Cochran formula allows a researcher to calculate an ideal sample size given a desired level of precision, desired confidence level, and the estimated proportion of the attribute present in the population.

The formula is given below:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample Size

n₀ = Representative Sample for Proportion

N = Total Population

Z² = The abscissa of the normal curve = 1.96

p = Proportion of success in the population from pilot survey = 0.5

q = Proportion of failure in the population from pilot survey = 0.5

e = error estimate = 0.05

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5 \times 0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n_0 = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025}$$

$$n_0 = 384.16$$

$$\text{Therefore, } n = \frac{384.16}{1 + \frac{(384.16 - 1)}{212}}$$

$$n = \frac{384.16}{2.81}$$

$$n = 137$$

In order to get a good representation of the population, the researcher used the stratified random sampling techniques. To make a sample a true representation of the parent population, the researcher first divided the entire population into homogenous groups called strata. By applying the systematic sampling, she selected items from each stratum into the sampling. Using this method, the researcher selected items out of a population of staff.

The formula for proportional sampling is given by Bourley as thus.

$$= \frac{N_h n}{N}$$

Where: N_h = Respondents/categories
 n = sample size
 N = Total population

Enugu North

$$= \frac{137 \times 76}{212} = 49$$

Enugu South

$$= \frac{137 \times 78}{212} = 50$$

Enugu East

$$= \frac{137 \times 58}{212} = 38$$

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The analysis of data relating to waste management system was carried out using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using Ordinal Linear-by-Linear Association model (Log-Linear Regression Model).

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

This chapter presents the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the data collected from the questionnaire. The collected questionnaires were checked for consistency before being coded. SPSS version 23 platform was used to facilitate analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages were used to analyze general information. Mean was used to analyze the study. Regression analysis was then used to investigate waste management system in Nigeria.

4.1 Response Rate

Fig 4.1. Response Rate

The total copies of questionnaire distributed were 137 but the study received a total of 118 duly completed copies of the questionnaire which constituted a response rate of 86 percent. De Vaus, (2013) informs that a response rate of 80 per cent and above is considered adequate. This implies that response rate for the study was adequate to enable the researcher to perform the analyses. Therefore, there were a total 86 respondents from the returned and completely filled copies of questionnaire.

4.1 Data Analysis

Bio data

The respondents were asked to provide general information as regard to Gender and Age Bracket. The analysis of this information is presented in this section

Gender of Respondents

The study sought to identify the gender of the respondents that took part in the research

Table 4.1.1: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	55	63.95	63.95	63.95
Female	31	36.05	36.05	100.0
Total	86	100.0	100.0	
Missing System	0	0.0		
Total	86	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23.0

Table 4.1.1 showed that there are 55 male respondents representing 63.95% while there are 31 female respondents representing 36.05%. The significance of this is that gender parity was achieved during the study.

The data in table 4.1.1 depicts the gender of the respondents. This was collected and analyzed to ascertain the gender of the respondents.

Age Bracket Respondents

Table 4.1.2: Age

Age bracket in years		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 – 25	12	13.95	13.95	13.95
	26 – 30	15	17.44	17.44	31.39
	31 – 35	18	20.93	20.93	52.32
	36 – 40	21	24.42	24.42	76.74
	41 and above	20	23.26	23.26	100.0
Total	86	100.0	100.0		
Missing	System	0	0.0		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23.0

Table 4.1.2 shows that majority of the respondents were between the ages of 36 and 41 years and above. Specifically, 12 respondents representing 13.95 percent of them were between 20-25 years, 15 respondents representing 17.44 per cent were between 26-30 years, 18 respondents representing 20.93 percent were between 31 – 35 years, 21 respondents representing 24.42 percent were between 36 – 40 years while 20 respondents representing 23.26 percent were from 41 years and above. This implies that majority of the respondents were of the right age and are knowledgeable on the efficacy of performance evaluations.

The data in table 4.1.2 focused on the age of the respondents. It was documented to ensure the respondents are old enough to be acquainted with the research being carried out.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

The Researcher conducted a multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables.

Decision Rule:

Reject the null hypothesis when the Sig. value is less than 0.05, otherwise accept the null hypothesis.

4.2.1 Assessment of waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis

Table 4.2.1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.115 ^a	.730	-.151	.55528

a. Predictors: (Constant), Assessment of waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis.

Table 4.2.2: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.025	1	.025	3.081	.005 ^b
	Residual	1.850	6	.308		
	Total	1.875	7			

a. Dependent Variable: waste management system

b. Predictors: (Constant), Assessment of waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis

Table 4.2.1 above showed that the R² is 73%. The R² is used to explain the goodness of fit. Therefore, since it is about 73%, it implies that about 73% change in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable and the higher the R² the better fit the independent variable.

Table 4.2.2 showed that the F – statistics is 3.081 while the Sig. value is 0.005. This shows that the model is significant and has a high goodness of fit.

Table 4.2.3: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.750	.481		3.639	.61
	Assessment of waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis	-.050	.176	-.115	-.285	.785

a. Dependent Variable: waste management system

Decision

Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the probability value is less than 0.05, table 4.3.3 shows that the probability value is 0.61. We accept the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that waste collection, treatment, and disposal systems across Enugu metropolis are not efficient.

4.3.2 Challenges bedeviling waste management practices in Nigeria.

Table 4.2.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.417 ^a	.874	.036	.50819

a. Predictors: (Constant), Waste management system

Table 4.2.5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.325	1	.325	4.260	.015 ^b
	Residual	1.550	6	.258		
	Total	1.875	7			

a. Dependent Variable: efficiency of employees

b. Predictors: (Constant), Waste management system

Table 4.2.4 above showed that the R^2 is 87%. The R^2 is used to explain the goodness of fit. Therefore, since it is about 87%, it implies that about 87% change in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables and the higher the R^2 the better fit the independent variables.

Table 4.2.5 showed that the F – statistics is 3.081 while the Sig. value is 0.015. This shows that the model is significant and has a high goodness of fit.

Table 4.2.6: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.027	.401		5.059	.002
	Challenges bedeviling waste management practices in Nigeria	-.153	.136	-.417	-1.123	.305

a. Dependent Variable: Waste management system

Decision

Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the probability value is less than 0.05, table 4.3.6 shows that the probability value is 0.002. We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that there are significant challenges bedeviling waste management practices in Nigeria.

Summary

Solid waste generation and management is a problem in developing nations and even in some developed ones but the consequences are more adverse with developing nations like Nigeria. This is because integrated solid waste management is a serious challenge to implement in such nations owing to some significant factors like poor funding, corruption from the political elites, overwhelming population growth, rapid urbanization, inadequate sensitization campaigns, poor technological knowhow, etc.

It is therefore recommended that addressing the challenges of waste management in Nigeria necessitates the need for an all-inclusive waste management approach. Proper implementation and enforcement of waste management laws and policies, review of the current waste management legislation across the states of the nation, private-public participation should be encouraged, adequate budgetary provision, periodic comprehensive appraisal of the environmental effect of waste management practices, knowledge sharing on global issues affecting ecological conditions and sustainable development.

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